

Usage of Social-Media for Sourcing Agricultural Information among Youth Farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the use of social media for sourcing agricultural information among youth farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 120 respondents, and data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents were young (mean age = 32 years), well-educated (78.3% had tertiary education), and digitally aware. WhatsApp (95%), YouTube (78.3%), and TikTok (78.3%) were the most accessible and intensively used platforms for agricultural purposes. Key information sourced included market prices (MS = 2.95), job opportunities (MS = 2.83), and weather updates (MS = 2.81), reflecting a strong economic and climate-smart orientation. Despite high awareness levels (95.8%), practical digital skills such as identifying credible content and applying knowledge were less prevalent. Major constraints included difficulty in finding relevant content, identifying credible sources, and language or contextual mismatches. Regression analysis revealed that marital status and income significantly influenced social media usage. The study concludes that although youth farmers are willing and able to use social media for agricultural information, critical digital literacy gaps and content limitations hinder optimal usage. Interventions should focus on localized, credible content and targeted digital training programs.

Keywords: Social-media, Agricultural information, Youth farmers, Digital literacy

INTRODUCTION

Social media without doubt has been a tool of great necessity in the modern society harboring the good and side effects and as well-being a transformative tool beyond its use in communication, in various sectors of economic empowerment (Kumari, 2020). Social media platforms like YouTube and others are widely used among farmers to get information, upload videos of their farming activities for the benefit of other people's benefits and also showcase or advertise their farm produce (Alotibi & Dabiah, 2022).

Agricultural information is an essential tool in modern day agricultural practice regardless of the field of practice. It serves as a reliable tool of communication between stakeholders, a channel for assessing trends and critical decision making (Adejo & Opeyemi, 2019). Information in agriculture is not a new trend as information dissemination in agriculture has always existed through mode of communications such as farm and home visits, the use of contact farmers, mass media and so on (Olaniyi, 2013) but the presence of social media eases dissemination of vital information among farmers.

Youth farmers in later generations of technology are well aware of the various available social media platforms as well as their applications (Adejo & Opeyemi, 2019). In sourcing agricultural information, social media among youth farmers are friendlier options due to the availability and easy accessibility of direct connection through mobile phones (Kanu,

2024). However, it is regarded with some people to be unsafe and part of online information are prone to falsehood which may easily sway ignorant individuals but social media are considered viable sources when the right channels are accessed (Oluyaire, *et al.*, 2020).

In the era of digital transformation, access to timely and relevant agricultural information remains a cornerstone for enhancing productivity, market access, and resilience among farmers. This is especially critical for youth farmers, who are often more exposed to technological tools and social media platforms than their older counterparts. Despite the proliferation of platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok which can serve as low-cost channels for disseminating agricultural knowledge there is still a disconnect between the availability of these platforms and their optimal usage for sourcing agricultural information in Nigeria.

In Kwara State, where agriculture plays a vital role in youth employment and food production, many young farmers continue to face challenges related to limited access to extension services, outdated farming practices, fluctuating market prices, and climate-related threats. Traditionally, these challenges were addressed through physical extension visits and radio broadcasts, but such methods have proven inadequate in meeting the dynamic information needs of today's youth. With increasing smartphone penetration and internet access, social media may present a potential alternative or complementary source of agricultural information. However, the extent to which youth

farmers utilize these platforms for agricultural purposes remains poorly understood.

Anecdotal evidence suggests that while youth are highly active on social media, much of their engagement may revolve around entertainment, lifestyle, and non-farm-related content. Therefore, the study seeks to bridge the knowledge gap by assessing the usage patterns, types of information sourced, and perceived effectiveness of social media platforms among youth farmers in Kwara State. It also explores the socio-economic and institutional factors influencing usage, as well as the barriers that limit its full adoption for agricultural purposes.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to assess the usage of social media in sourcing agricultural information by youth farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the youth farmers;
2. identify the available social media tools for sourcing agricultural information by the youth farmers;
3. examine the level of use of social media for sourcing agricultural information by the respondents;
4. identify the kinds of agricultural information sourced on social media by the respondents;
5. examine the knowledge level of the youth farmers on social media for sourcing agricultural information; and
6. identify the constraints faced by the youth farmers in using social media to source for agricultural information.

Hypothesis

H01: There is no significant relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics and the level of usage of social media in sourcing agricultural information by the youth farmers.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Kwara State, Nigeria. The population for this study included all the youth farmers between the ages of 15-40 years old in the selected Local Government Areas of Kwara State, Nigeria. A

three-stage sampling technique was used for this study; the first stage involved a purposive selection of three (3) LGAs from Kwara State where social media platforms are widely adopted which are Ilorin South, Ilorin West and Offa LGAs. The second stage involved a random selection of four communities from each of the selected LGAs giving a total of twelve (12) communities and the third and final stage involved a random selection of ten (10) youth farmers in each of the selected communities making a total of 120 respondents used for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The mean age of the respondent is 32 years, several studies of digital technology adoption across Africa have found youth to be the earliest and most active adopters, as they tend to be more tech-savvy and open to new innovations. A 2020 study of mobile internet use in Nigeria reported 72% of 18-35-years old were users, compared to just 32% of those over 35 years old (Adeola *et al.* 2020). (Motti & Kabanda, 2019) also reported that youth have been found to use digital platforms for a diversity of activities like entertainment, news, socializing and business/commerce. There is a relatively balanced population between male and female youths. Result shows that (53.8%) were males while (46.2%) were females, this balance suggests a positive trend towards gender equality in agricultural participation. This finding is contrary to the report of (Olatinwo *et al.*, 2017) that 90% of the rural youths are male. Majority (78.3%) of the respondents had tertiary education, 12.5% had secondary education while 6.7% had no formal education. This result implies that majority of the respondents were literate with a high level of education and are likely to be receptive to change and adoption of innovations like the use of ICT to source for information. (Kassie *et al.*, 2019; Rondon *et al.*, 2017), identified higher education levels as a key factor associated with increased technology usage and innovation adoption among farmers and agribusinesses in developing country contexts, including Nigeria.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on their socio-economic characteristics

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	Standard deviation
Age				
20-30	59	49.2	32years	5.130
31-40	61	50.8		
Sex				
Male	64	53.8		
Female	56	46.2		
Marital Status				
Single	60	50.0		
Married	43	35.8		
Separated	7	5.8		
Divorced	5	4.2		
Widowed	5	4.2		
Household size			5persons	1.927
1-5	73	60.8		
6-10	47	39.2		
Level of Education				
No formal	8	6.7		
Primary	3	2.5		
Secondary	15	12.5		
Tertiary	94	78.3		
Secondary Occupation				
Farming	31	25.8		
Teaching	6	5.0		
Trading	14	11.7		
Other	69	57.5		
Annual Income			₦731,417	825354.821
₦100,000- ₦500,000	54	45.0		
₦501,000- ₦1,000,000	56	46.7		
₦1,001,000- ₦5,000,000	9	7.5		
>₦5,000,000	1	0.8		

Source: Field survey, 2025

Available social media platforms

Findings from Table 2 reveals the social media platforms available to the respondents for sourcing agricultural information. WhatsApp (95.0%) rank 1st as the most available platforms. YouTube (78.3%) and TikTok (78.3%) both rank 2nd and this confirms the dominance of instant messaging and visual platforms

in rural communication. FAO (2021) noted WhatsApp’s simplicity and multimedia capabilities make it ideal for agricultural extension. Similarly, YouTube and TikTok have grown as learning hubs, especially among younger, educated farmers. Zoom (30.0%) and LinkedIn (26.7%) rank lowest among the social media platforms available to the respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on the available social media platforms

Platforms	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Facebook	88	73.3	4 th
Instagram	91	75.8	3 rd
X (Twitter)	72	60.0	5 th
WhatsApp	114	95.0	1 st
YouTube	94	78.3	2 nd
TikTok	94	78.3	2 nd
Zoom	36	30.0	7 th
LinkedIn	32	26.7	8 th
Telegram	70	59.3	6 th

Source: Field survey, 2025

***Multiple responses

Level of Use of Social-Media for Sourcing Agricultural Information

Results from Table 3 shows the level of usage of social media platforms indicates that WhatsApp (MS=2.93), YouTube (MS=2.92) and TikTok (MS=2.67) were the most used social media platforms for sourcing agricultural information by the respondents. WhatsApp ranks first in both availability and usage intensity for agricultural information sourcing is consistent with multiple studies, research has consistently shown that WhatsApp's popularity stems from its low data consumption, multimedia capabilities, and group communication features that facilitate peer-to-peer learning among farmers. YouTube's second ranking in usage intensity despite having fewer users than Instagram and TikTok suggests that those who use YouTube do so more intensively for agricultural information. This pattern

aligns with research indicating that "YouTube videos are most popular for information getting with applications," highlighting the platform's role in providing detailed, visual agricultural content that is particularly valuable for learning farming techniques. The high availability of Instagram (75.8%) and TikTok (78.3%) but relatively lower usage scores for agricultural information suggests these platforms may be used more for social engagement than serious agricultural learning. This finding reflects the broader challenge of information quality and relevance on entertainment-focused platforms. The least used platforms were Zoom (MS=1.88) and LinkedIn (MS=1.73) as being professional or formal platforms, are less favored by youth farmers due to interface complexity or low relevance to agricultural discussions.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents based on their level of use of social media for sourcing agricultural information

Tools	Never F (%)	Rarely F (%)	Often F (%)	Always F (%)	Mean score	Rank
Facebook	27(22.7)	31(26.1)	28(23.5)	33(27.7)	2.56	4 th
Instagram	25(20.8)	39(32.5)	30(25.0)	26(21.7)	2.48	5 th
X (Twitter)	33(27.7)	30(25.2)	26(21.8)	30(25.2)	2.45	6 th
WhatsApp	18(15.0)	25(20.8)	24(20.0)	53(44.2)	2.93	1 st
YouTube	11(9.2)	28(23.5)	40(33.6)	40(33.6)	2.92	2 nd
TikTok	24(20.3)	27(22.9)	31(26.3)	36(30.5)	2.67	3 rd
Zoom	52(43.3)	40(33.3)	18(15.0)	10(8.3)	1.88	8 th
LinkedIn	62(51.7)	35(29.2)	16(13.3)	7(5.8)	1.73	9 th
Telegram	44(36.7)	33(27.5)	26(21.7)	17(14.2)	2.13	7 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Kinds of Agricultural Information Sourced

Table 4 provides the result for the kinds of agricultural information sourced by the respondents on social media platforms. The ranking of market information as the most sought-after content (MS=2.95) reflects the commercial orientation of the respondents and aligns with literature emphasizing the importance of market access for smallholder farmers. This reflects youths' interest in economic empowerment and adaptive planning. Ojebuyi & Salawu (2020) noted that farmers prioritize market price updates and employment resources. Job opportunities (MS=2.83) rank 2nd and this suggest that the respondents are actively using social media to explore opportunities beyond traditional crop production. The high interest

in job opportunities reflects the broader employment challenges facing youth in agricultural sectors with 91.7% of the respondents earning between N100,000-N1,000,000 annually, many are likely seeking additional income sources or better employment prospects within the agricultural value chain. Weather and climate updates ranking 3rd (MS=2.81) reflects the critical importance of climate information in agricultural decision-making. This finding is consistent with research showing that timely weather information can significantly improve crop planning and risk management strategies among farmers. Loans and grants information (MS=2.36) was the least information sourced on social media by the respondents.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents based on the kinds of agricultural information sourced on social media

Social Medias	Never F (%)	Rarely F (%)	Often F (%)	Always F (%)	Means score	Rank
Weather and Climate updates	20(16.9)	24(20.3)	32(27.1)	42(35.6)	2.81	3 rd
Market Information	11(9.3)	27(22.9)	37(31.4)	43(36.4)	2.95	1 st
Farming practices and seed information	14(11.7)	36(30.0)	45(37.5)	25(20.8)	2.68	7 th
Agricultural Extension Services	10(8.3)	43(35.8)	42(35.0)	25(20.8)	2.68	7 th
Input supply information	8(6.7)	39(32.5)	52(43.3)	21(17.5)	2.72	5 th
Agribusiness information	16(13.3)	30(25.0)	50(41.7)	24(20.0)	2.68	7 th
Job opportunities	9(7.5)	39(32.5)	35(29.2)	37(30.8)	2.83	2 nd
Consumer preferences and feedback	7(5.8)	43(35.8)	46(38.3)	24(20.0)	2.73	4 th
Research findings and innovations	10(8.3)	44(36.7)	39(32.5)	27(22.5)	2.69	6 th
Loans and grants information	27(22.5)	38(31.8)	40(33.3)	15(12.5)	2.36	10 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Knowledge Level of Use of Social-Media for Sourcing Agricultural Information

Result from Table 5 shows the knowledge of the respondents on social media usage. The knowledge result reveals impressive awareness levels, with over 95% knowing that social media can be used for agricultural information access. However, the declining percentages for more technical skills (67.2% can recognize false information, 68.3% can apply knowledge obtained) indicate a need for digital literacy training programs. The finding that only 67.2% can recognize false or misleading agricultural

information online is particularly concerning given the prevalence of misinformation on social media platforms. This gap in critical evaluation skills poses risks for agricultural decision-making and highlights the need for media literacy programs in agricultural extension. The result shows that awareness is strong, but critical literacy and application remain weak. UNESCO (2022) highlights the danger of misinformation in digital agriculture. Ajayi *et al.* (2022) recommend digital literacy training that focuses on content verification and practical application.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents based on their knowledge level of use of social media for sourcing agricultural information

Statements	Frequency	Percentage
Do you know that social media platforms can be used to access agricultural information?	114	95.8
Do you understand how social media can improve your knowledge of modern farming technique?	94	78.3
Can you identify credible sources of agricultural information on social media?	88	73.3
Do you know how to join agricultural groups or follow farming pages on Facebook, WhatsApp, or Telegram?	87	72.5
Can you search for specific agricultural topics on YouTube or Instagram using relevant keywords or hashtags?	93	77.5
Do you know how to subscribe or follow farming content creators or extension agents online?	83	69.2
Do you know that agricultural information on social media includes market prices, weather updates, pest control tips, and government programs?	99	82.5
Do you understand the difference between entertainment content and educational agricultural content on social media?	97	80.8
Can you recognize false or misleading agricultural information online?	80	67.2
Do you know how to apply agricultural knowledge obtained from social media to farming practices?	82	68.3
Do you know you can share useful agricultural content from social media with other farmers	90	75.0
Do you know how to download, save, or bookmark farming related contents for future reference?	81	67.5

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Constraints Faced in Using Social-Media for Sourcing Agricultural Information

The mean score on constraints experienced in using social media platforms in sourcing for agricultural information is presented in Table 6. Result shows that inability to search for relevant agricultural content (MS=2.56) rank 1st and this suggest that the primary barriers are skill-based rather than purely infrastructural. difficulty identifying credible sources of information (MS=2.53) rank 2nd aligning with literature concerns about information quality on social media platforms. This finding underscores the need for trusted agricultural information networks and

verification systems. Agricultural content not available in local languages ranking 3rd (MS=2.50) and irrelevant or non-contextual agricultural information (MS=2.48) ranking 5th highlight the importance of localized content creation. This shows that information navigation and critical evaluation, rather than technical access, are the main barriers. These findings echo FAO & CTA (2020), which emphasized that youth-friendly content and local language availability are essential for effective digital extension. Poor connectivity (1.85), and privacy concerns (1.98) amongst others were the least severe challenges faced by the respondents in their usage of

social media platforms in sourcing for agricultural information.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents based on the constraints faced in using social media for sourcing agricultural information

Constraints	VS	S	NS	NC	Means score	Rank
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
Poor internet connectivity	53(44.2)	38(31.7)	23(19.2)	6(5.0)	1.85	16 th
High cost of internet data	39(32.8)	48(40.3)	19(16.2)	13(10.9)	2.05	13 th
Limited access to smartphones or digital devices	24(20.0)	42(35.0)	32(26.7)	22(18.3)	2.43	8 th
Frequent power outages	39(32.5)	49(40.8)	20(16.7)	12(10.0)	2.04	14 th
Lack of digital literacy or technical skills	26(21.8)	31(26.1)	40(33.6)	22(18.5)	2.49	4 th
Inability to search for relevant agricultural content	21(17.5)	40(33.3)	30(25.4)	29(24.2)	2.56	1 st
Difficulty identifying credible sources of information	17(14.4)	46(39.0)	30(25.4)	25(21.2)	2.53	2 nd
Limited awareness of agricultural pages/groups to follow	26(21.7)	36(30.0)	37(30.8)	21(17.5)	2.44	7 th
Misinformation or fake news on social media	36(30.3)	36(30.0)	28(23.5)	19(16.0)	2.25	12 th
Agricultural content not available in local languages	22(18.3)	42(35.0)	30(25.0)	26(21.7)	2.50	3 rd
Irrelevant or non-contextual agricultural information	19(15.8)	43(35.8)	39(32.5)	19(15.8)	2.48	5 th
Overload of entertainment content distracting from useful agricultural posts	29(24.2)	33(27.5)	36(30.0)	22(18.3)	2.43	8 th
Privacy concerns or fear of online scams	48(40.0)	40(33.3)	18(15.0)	14(11.7)	1.98	15 th
Time constraints due to other farming activities	17(14.2)	59(49.2)	35(29.2)	9(7.5)	2.30	11 th
Incompatibility of some platforms with local needs or farming systems	29(24.2)	40(33.3)	33(27.5)	18(15.0)	2.33	10 th
Lack of interactive engagement with experts on platforms	24(20.0)	37(30.8)	36(30.0)	23(19.2)	2.48	5 th

Source: Field survey, 2025

VS = Very severe, S = Severe, NS = Not severe, NC = Not a constraint

Result of the Tested Hypotheses

Table 7: Linear regression showing relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics and the level of use of social media for sourcing agricultural information.

Predictors	Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
(Constant)	13.939	4.107	3.394	.001
Age	-.030	.095	-.306	.760
Sex	-.014	.865	-.156	.877
Marital Status	.304	.472	3.035	.003
Household Size	.061	.238	.662	.509
Level of Education	.161	.568	1.643	.103
Income	.195	.366	2.030	.045

Source: Field Survey, 2025

R² = .142, Adjusted r square = .086, F = 2.531

Findings from Table 7 shows the linear regression analysis examining the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and the level of social media use for sourcing agricultural information. Marital status demonstrated the strongest relationship with usage behavior ($\beta = 0.304$, $p = 0.003$), indicating that different marital categories are associated with varying levels of social media engagement for agricultural information purposes. This finding suggests that married farmers may have different information needs compared to their single counterparts, possibly driven by household-level decision-making responsibilities, family food security considerations, or expanded social networks that facilitate information sharing. The significance of marital status as a predictor highlights the social dimensions of information-seeking behavior, where family structures and responsibilities may influence how actively individuals pursue agricultural knowledge through digital platforms. Income level also emerged as a significant predictor of social media usage ($\beta = 0.195$, $p = 0.045$), demonstrating a positive relationship where higher-income farmers exhibit greater engagement with social media for agricultural information. This relationship likely reflects the economic barriers to technology adoption, where farmers with higher incomes have better access to smartphones, reliable internet connectivity, and data packages necessary for sustained social media engagement. Furthermore, higher-income farmers may be more commercially oriented in their farming operations, creating greater demand for timely market information, technical

updates, and business intelligence that social media platforms can provide.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that youth farmers in Kwara State exhibit high awareness and moderate usage of social media for agricultural purposes, with WhatsApp, YouTube, and TikTok being the dominant platforms. Despite widespread access and willingness to use these platforms, critical gaps remain in digital literacy, content evaluation, and contextual application. The findings suggest a disconnect between the high potential of social media as a transformative agricultural tool and the current capability of youth to fully exploit it. Socioeconomic factors such as education and income remain significant enablers, while the quality and relevance of available content, as well as the skills to navigate it, act as key constraints. It is therefore recommended that the government, through agricultural extension agencies, in collaboration with NGOs, should organize regular training workshops to improve youth farmers' skills in searching for relevant agricultural content, identifying credible sources, and applying information from social media platforms to real-life farming practices. Also, development partners should invest in creating and promoting official social media handles, pages, and WhatsApp broadcast groups that deliver timely, verified agricultural information such as market prices, weather alerts, extension tips, and funding opportunities

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